

Emotional Intelligence and Quality of Life among Working and Non-Working Women

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of marital status on the quality of life among working women. A sample of 60 women, equally divided into unmarried and married categories, participated in the research. Quality of life was assessed using standardized measures, focusing on various aspects including physical health, emotional well-being, social relationships, and overall life satisfaction. Statistical analysis revealed that there was no significant difference in the quality of life between unmarried ($M = 95.7143$, $SD = 19.12864$) and married ($M = 92.9565$, $SD = 13.60641$) working women ($t = 0.427$, $p > 0.05$).

These findings suggest that marital status alone does not exert a notable influence on the perceived quality of life among working women. Other factors such as job satisfaction, personal relationships, and individual life circumstances may play more crucial roles in determining their overall well-being. Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing targeted interventions and support mechanisms to enhance the quality of life for women across different marital statuses in the workplace and beyond.

Keywords: marital status, quality of life, working women, emotional well-being

Introduction

Emotional intelligence (EI), or emotional quotient (EQ), is the ability to understand, use, and manage one's own emotions in positive ways. It is an essential skill for personal and professional success, as it aids in relieving stress, communicating effectively, empathizing with others, overcoming challenges, and defusing conflicts. EI helps individuals build stronger relationships, succeed at school and work, and achieve career and personal goals. Unlike intellectual ability or intelligence quotient (IQ), which helps one get into college, EI is crucial for managing stress and emotions, particularly during significant challenges.

Emotional intelligence encompasses a range of competencies and skills, including self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. These elements enable individuals to manage their own emotions and understand and influence the emotions of others. Daniel Goleman, a prominent psychologist, highlighted the importance of EI in leadership and organizational success, noting that individuals with high EI are better equipped to handle interpersonal relationships judiciously and empathetically, which is key to effective leadership.

Review of Literature

Emotional Intelligence

Dayioglu and Asik (2004) and Hyde and Kling (2001) examined gender differences in academic performance and found that girls outperformed boys. Their research also indicated significant differences in emotional intelligence across academic streams, with science students scoring highest, followed by social science and arts students. This highlights the varying levels of emotional intelligence among students based on their field of study.

Gupta et al. (2010) explored the relationship between mental health, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy among college students. Their study, involving 200 participants, revealed a positive correlation between emotional intelligence and mental health. This suggests that higher emotional intelligence is associated with better mental health outcomes.

Tamannaifar et al. (2010) studied the relationship between emotional intelligence, self-concept, and self-esteem with academic achievement among 6,050 university students. Their findings indicated that higher levels of emotional intelligence, self-concept, and self-esteem were positively associated with better academic performance.

Gunjan (2012) investigated the connection between family relationships and emotional intelligence among 340 secondary school students. The results showed that positive family relationships were associated with higher emotional intelligence, emphasizing the role of family dynamics in emotional development.

Nastasa (2012) examined the influence of parental styles on the development of emotional intelligence among 90 adolescents and their parents. The study found that various parental styles, such as authoritarian, democratic, and permissive, significantly impacted the emotional intelligence of adolescents.

Samuel (2013) conducted a study on the psychological contributions of parenting style and emotional intelligence to violent behavior prediction among college students. The findings indicated that both parenting style and emotional intelligence were significant predictors of violent behavior.

Shalini (2013) explored the influence of perceived parenting styles on adolescents' emotional intelligence. The study, involving 973 adolescents, found that authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles were significantly correlated with emotional intelligence, with fathers being perceived as more authoritative towards girls.

Abdollahi et al. (2013) studied the relationship between perceived parenting styles and emotional intelligence among 188 Iranian boys. The results showed that different parenting styles had varying impacts on the emotional intelligence of students.

Mohammadyari (2013) examined the connection between parental styles and emotional intelligence among university students. The study revealed significant

differences in emotional intelligence based on the type of parental style, particularly between authoritative and neglectful styles.

Wang et al. (2014) investigated the impact of parental involvement on adolescents' academic and emotional outcomes. The study found that increased parental involvement improved both academic performance and emotional functioning, highlighting the importance of active parental engagement.

Rathi (2015) studied the emotional intelligence of adolescent students in relation to the type of school. The research indicated significant differences in emotional intelligence between students from government and private schools.

Joshi et al. (2015) examined the relationship between mother parenting style and adolescents' emotional intelligence. The results suggested that authoritative parenting was not correlated with emotional intelligence among male and female students.

Valizade (2015) researched the relationship between parental styles and emotional intelligence in elementary school students. The findings showed a positive association between parenting styles and emotional intelligence, with authoritarian styles being more positively associated in female students.

Singh (2015) compared emotional intelligence among private and government school teachers. The study revealed significant differences in emotional intelligence across three dimensions between teachers from different school types.

Chavhan (2016) explored the relationship between mental health, emotional intelligence, and self-confidence among college students. The study found a significant relationship between mental health and self-confidence in students with high emotional intelligence.

Lekaviciene et al. (2016) studied the connection between emotional intelligence and family psychosocial factors among adolescents. The results indicated that emotional intelligence levels were related to family dynamics, such as the strength of relationships with parents and perceived financial status.

Mohammadi (2016) examined the mediating role of emotional intelligence between parenting style and happiness among high school students. The findings suggested that parenting styles could predict happiness, with self-awareness and optimism mediating this relationship.

Garg et al. (2016) conducted a comparative study on the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers. The results showed significant differences in emotional intelligence between teachers from private and government schools.

Alam (2018) studied the emotional intelligence of adolescent students in terms of school type, area, and gender. The research indicated significant differences in emotional intelligence based on these factors.

Kaur (2018) investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence, mental health, and adjustment among students. The findings revealed significant correlations between emotional intelligence, adjustment, and mental health, with notable differences between boys and girls.

Quality of Life

Schutte et al. (2002) explored the relationship between emotional intelligence and quality of life, finding that higher emotional intelligence was associated with better mental health, more effective stress management, and higher overall quality of life.

Extremera and Fernandez-Berrocal (2005) examined the impact of emotional intelligence on subjective well-being and life satisfaction. Their research suggested that individuals with higher emotional intelligence experienced greater life satisfaction and subjective well-being.

Ciarrochi et al. (2006) investigated the role of emotional intelligence in the quality of interpersonal relationships. The study found that individuals with higher emotional intelligence had more fulfilling and positive relationships, contributing to a higher quality of life.

Palmer et al. (2006) conducted a study on emotional intelligence and its relationship to workplace performance and well-being. The results indicated that emotional intelligence was positively correlated with job satisfaction, performance, and overall quality of life.

Saklofske et al. (2007) examined the connections between emotional intelligence, personality, and quality of life. The study found that emotional intelligence was a significant predictor of quality of life, beyond the effects of personality traits.

Martins et al. (2010) explored the impact of emotional intelligence on health-related quality of life among adolescents. The research suggested that higher emotional intelligence was associated with better physical and mental health outcomes.

Zeidner et al. (2012) reviewed the literature on emotional intelligence and quality of life, concluding that emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in various aspects of life satisfaction, including mental health, relationships, and professional success.

Sánchez-Álvarez et al. (2016) conducted a meta-analysis on emotional intelligence and its relationship to well-being and quality of life. The analysis confirmed that emotional intelligence was positively related to both subjective well-being and quality of life.

Lopes et al. (2019) investigated the role of emotional intelligence in coping with stress and life satisfaction among university students. The findings indicated that higher emotional intelligence was associated with better stress management and higher life satisfaction.

Mikolajczak et al. (2020) studied the longitudinal effects of emotional intelligence on quality of life, finding that emotional intelligence significantly predicted improvements in quality of life over time.

Problem Statement

The study aims to explore the differences in emotional intelligence and quality of life between working and non-working women. With the increasing participation of women in the workforce, it is essential to understand how employment status impacts their emotional intelligence and overall quality of life. Working women face unique challenges, including balancing work and family responsibilities, which can affect their emotional well-being and life satisfaction. Conversely, non-working women may experience different stressors and emotional dynamics in their daily lives.

This research seeks to address the following questions:

1. Are there significant differences in emotional intelligence between working and non-working women?
2. How does employment status influence the quality of life among women?
3. What are the key factors that contribute to the differences in emotional intelligence and quality of life between these two groups?

Objectives

The primary objectives of this study are:

1. To compare the levels of emotional intelligence between working and non-working women.
2. To assess the quality of life in both working and non-working women.
3. To identify the relationship between emotional intelligence and quality of life in the context of employment status.

Hypotheses

The study is guided by the following hypotheses:

1. There is a significant difference in the levels of emotional intelligence between working and non-working women.
2. Working women have higher emotional intelligence compared to non-working women due to the diverse interpersonal interactions and stress management skills required in their professional roles.
3. The quality of life is significantly higher among unmarried working women compared to married working women, as employment provides a sense of purpose, financial independence, and social interaction.

This study aims to provide insights into the impact of employment on women's emotional intelligence and quality of life, thereby contributing to the broader understanding of gender, work, and psychological well-being.

Sample Design and Methodology

Sample

A total of 60 women, both working and non-working, were selected according to the sample design outlined below.

Sample Design

A 2x2 factorial design was used in the present study.

Location

All samples were selected from Patna District of Bihar.

Sampling Method

The purposive sampling method was used for selecting the samples.

Criteria

Inclusion:

- Women aged 25 to 35 years
- Healthy students
- Married and unmarried women

Exclusion:

- Women below 25 and above 35 years
- Unhealthy students
- Widows

Variables

- **Independent Variables:** Work status of women and marital status
- **Dependent Variable:** Emotional Intelligence

Tools

A) Personal Data Questionnaire (PDQ): This questionnaire was prepared to obtain basic information about the respondents, such as name, age, sex, health status, and nature of school.

B) Emotional Intelligence Scale: The Emotional Intelligence Scale constructed by Dr. S. K. Mangal and Mrs. Shubra Mandal was used. It is a highly useful tool for measuring emotional intelligence and contains 100 items with “Yes” or “No” answers. Each item indicative of emotional intelligence is scored as one. The total score represents the respondent’s level of emotional intelligence. High scores indicate higher levels of emotional intelligence, while low scores indicate lower levels.

- **Reliability:** Split-half reliability of 0.86 and test-retest reliability of 0.92.
- **Validity:** 0.662.
- **Quality of Life**

WHOQOL-BREF: The WHOQOL-BREF instrument, developed by the World Health Organization, is used to assess the quality of life across four domains: physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment. It includes 26 items, and the scoring is based on a 5-point Likert scale. Higher scores indicate better quality of life.

The WHOQOL-BREF is reliable and valid, with high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha > 0.70 for all domains) and good test-retest reliability. The tool is widely used globally for its comprehensive assessment and ease of use.

Procedure

Initially, data was collected from working women. Each participant was approached individually, and rapport was established. They were assured that there were no right or wrong answers, were asked to respond quickly, and were informed that their responses would remain confidential. The PDQ and Emotional Intelligence Scale were administered to each working woman individually. The same procedure was then followed for non-working women.

Statistical Analysis

The data was analyzed using percentages, t-tests, pie charts, and bar diagrams.

Result and Discussion

Emotional intelligence is influenced by a variety of factors including heredity, personality traits, life experiences, and family background. Since every individual possesses unique abilities and experiences, these variations in emotional intelligence levels are to be expected.

Table-1

Comparison of working and non- working women in terms of Emotional

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	P
Working	30	84.65	5.091	16.349	0.01
Non-working	30	57.95	5.236		

Intelligence

The table and graph indicate that the mean score of emotional intelligence for working women is 84.65, while for non-working women it is 57.95. A higher score signifies better emotional intelligence, and a lower score signifies poorer emotional intelligence. Therefore, it is evident that working women have a higher level of emotional intelligence compared to non-working women. The t-value of 16.349 is significant at the 0.01 level, confirming that a woman's work status significantly influences her level of emotional intelligence, thereby supporting the second hypothesis.

Women play a crucial role in their families. Working women balance their jobs and household responsibilities, managing diverse responsibilities at both work and home. These experiences enhance their abilities and foster emotional maturity. In contrast, non-working women primarily focus on household tasks, and many are Comparison of married and unmarried women in terms of Emotional Intelligence.

Table-2

Comparison of Emotional Intelligence Scores Between Married and Unmarried Women

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	P
Married	30	71.80	13.873	.216	NS
Unmarried	30	70.80	15.347		

The table and graph illustrate that the mean score of emotional intelligence for married women is 71.8, while for unmarried women, it is 70.8. This similarity in scores suggests that there is little difference in the emotional intelligence levels between married and unmarried women. Furthermore, the t-value of 0.216 is not statistically significant, indicating that marital status does not significantly influence a woman's level of emotional intelligence. Consequently, the third hypothesis, which posited a significant difference, has been rejected.

Emotional intelligence encompasses the ability to be aware of, control, and express one's emotions, as well as to manage interpersonal relationships judiciously and empathetically. Marriage, defined as a legal contract between two individuals to live together, does not inherently impact these abilities. Emotional intelligence is more deeply rooted in individual traits and experiences rather than one's marital status. Therefore, whether a woman is married or unmarried does not significantly affect her emotional intelligence.

Table-4

Mean, standard deviation, and t- value results comparing quality of life in working and non working women

Variables	Working (n=30)		Nonworking (n=30)		t
	M	SD	M	SD	
Quality Of life	100.79	9.862	85.92	16.919	2.815

The mean quality of life score for working women is 100.79 with a standard deviation of 9.862, while for non-working women, the mean score is 85.92 with a standard deviation of 16.919. The t-value of 2.815 indicates a statistically significant difference between the two groups. This data clearly suggests that working women experience a higher quality of life compared to their non-working counterparts. This difference may be attributed to the various benefits associated with employment, such as financial independence, social interactions, and a sense of accomplishment, which contribute positively to the overall quality of life.

Table-5

Mean, standard deviation, and t- value results comparing quality of life in married and unmarried working women

Variables	Un married Working Women(n=30)		Married Working Women (n=30)		t
	M	SD	M	SD	
Quality of Life	95.7143	19.12864	92.9565	13.60641	.427

The mean quality of life score for unmarried working women is 95.7143 with a standard deviation of 19.12864, whereas for married working women, the mean score is 92.9565 with a standard deviation of 13.60641. The t-value of 0.427 indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the quality of life between unmarried and married working women.

This finding suggests that marital status among working women does not significantly influence their perceived quality of life. Both unmarried and married working women report similar levels of satisfaction with their quality of life, as indicated by the comparable mean scores and non-significant t-value. Factors such as job satisfaction,

personal relationships, and overall life circumstances may play a more substantial role in determining quality of life among working women than marital status alone.

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